

Colorimetric Determination of Ethylene Dibromide and its Application in Air, Water and Grain Samples

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1,2-Ethylene dibromide is widely used as antiknock additive in leaded gasoline¹ and also to control insects¹. Looking to the importance of ethylene dibromide, several methods for its determination have been reported in literature. Some of them are based on gas chromatography², high performance liquid chromatography³, gas liquid chromatography⁴ and polarography⁵. Spectrophotometric methods are based on the conversion of ethylene dibromide to inorganic bromide and its determination using *p*-rosaniline⁶ or indirect determination of ethylene dibromide using 4-nitrobenzenediazonium tetrafluoroborate⁷.

The present communication reports a simple method for the spectrophotometric determination of ethylene dibromide using fluorescein⁸. It is based on the conversion of ethylene dibromide to sodium bromide using metallic sodium. The sodium bromide thus formed is then reacted with *n*-chlorosuccinimide to liberate free bromine which gives a pink coloured eosin dye with fluorescein.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance spectra of eosin dye (2',4',5',7'-tetrabromofluorescein) showed maximum absorbance at 520 nm, where the reagent blank showed negligible absorbance.

Beer's law was obeyed in the range 20–160 μg of ethylene dibromide in 25 ml of final solution (0.8–6.4 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $4.3 \times 10^4 \pm 100 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.007 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing 40 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$ of ethylene dibromide for a period of eight days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.008 and 3.60% respectively.

About 2–3 min were required for conversion of ethylene dibromide to inorganic bromide and 10 min for complete colour development. The most suitable temperature for full colour reaction was within the range 20–35°. The optimum pH was found to be 5.5 ± 0.1 . It was found that 0.3–0.4 ml of fluorescein (9-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-6-hydroxy-3-isoxanthenone, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$) was sufficient for the complete colour reaction. Maximum and constant absorbance was observed when 1 ml of 0.5% *n*-chlorosuccinimide solution was used.

Effect of foreign species : Interference from iodide was masked with H_2O_2 to oxidise iodide into iodate⁹. Halogenated fumigants, e.g. 1,1-dichloro-1-nitroethane, ethylene dichloride and organophosphorus pesticides, e.g. dimethoate, phorate, parathion and ethion had no effect on colour development.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched silica cells was used. An air sampling train consisting of rotameter, vacuum pump, drying tube and impinger of 35 ml capacity were used for the determination of ethylene dibromide in air. All chemicals used were of AnalaR or similar grade.

A stock solution containing $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg dm}^{-3}$ ethylene dibromide (supplied by Indian Grain Storage Institute) was prepared in ethanol. Fluorescein solution was prepared by dissolving fluorescein (0.3 g) in 0.1 *N* NaOH solution (5 ml) and diluted to 1000 ml with water⁸. A 0.5% solution of *n*-chlorosuccinimide was prepared in distilled water. Buffer solution (pH 5.5 ± 0.1) was prepared by mixing 1 *M* sodium acetate solution (10 ml) with 1 *N* acetic acid (1 ml). Metallic sodium ($\sim 0.1 \text{ g}$) was used for the conversion of organic bromide to inorganic bromide. Double-distilled demineralised water was used throughout.

Procedure : A mixture of an alcoholic solution of ethylene dibromide (20–160 μg) and sodium metal ($\sim 0.1 \text{ g}$) was heated on a water-bath at 80–90° till the dissolution of sodium and evaporation of ethanol. The resulting residue was dissolved in deionised water and diluted as required. To it was added acetate buffer solution (1 ml) followed by 0.5% *n*-chlorosuccinimide solution (1 ml) to convert inorganic bromide into free bromine. Then fluorescein solution (0.3–0.4 ml) was added and the solution was kept for $\sim 10 \text{ min}$ for full colour development. The solution was made up to 25 ml and its absorbance measured at 520 nm against a reagent blank.

To check the validity of the method in determination of ethylene dibromide in air, water, wheat and rice samples, synthetic samples were prepared using 40 and 80 μg ethylene dibromide. The recovery ranged from 95–99%. Ethylene dibromide in air and grain samples was also determined by the present method and also by the earlier reported

method⁶. Results were found to be comparable. Ethylene dibromide can be precisely determined upto 0.8 ppm in air, water and grain samples by the proposed method.

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TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED METHOD WITH OTHER COLORIMETRIC/SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS

Sl. no.	Method/Reagent	λ max nm	Beer's law range/sensitivity	Remarks
1.	Conversion of ethylene dibromide to inorganic bromide and determination by <i>p</i> -rosaniline ^a	530	5–60 μ g	Less sensitive
2.	Determination by ethanolamine and 4-nitrobenzene diazonium ^b	510	70 μ g	Less sensitive
3.	Present method	520	0.8–6.4 ppm	More sensitive

^aRef. 6. ^bRef. 7.

The present method has also been compared with other colorimetric and spectrophotometric methods for the determination of ethylene dibromide (Table 1). The method was found to be comparatively simple and sensitive.

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